

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of G. R. or A. R. grade. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to maintain the ionic strength constant. The dioxane used for experimental work was purified¹.

The ligand, 4-methylphenacylidene anthranilic acid (I), was prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of 4-methylphenylglyoxalhydrate with anthranilic acid in ethanol on a steam bath for 3.5 hr. The reaction mixture was refrigerated and the solid product obtained was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol (m.p. 190°). Satisfactory elemental analysis were obtained.

The stock solutions of NaClO_4 , HClO_4 and NaOH were prepared in usual manner in double distilled water. All $p\text{H}$ measurements were carried out on a Philips PP 9040 $p\text{H}$ meter fitted with combination electrode single rod assembly PV 9014 (accuracy 0.1 $p\text{H}$). The instrument was standardised against 0.05 M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate for $p\text{H}$ 4. Following solutions were titrated separately against standard NaOH (0.1 M) at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ (i) free HClO_4 , (ii) free HClO_4 + ligand and (iii) metal-perchlorate in free HClO_4 + ligand. The ratio between the metal and the ligand was kept at 1 : 4 and the ionic strength of 0.1 M was maintained with appropriate amount of 1 M NaClO_4 .

Results and Discussion

From the $p\text{H}$ titration curves, the values $\bar{n}A$, \bar{n} and pL were obtained adopting the Irving-Rossotti technique². From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}A$ values at various $p\text{H}$ values were calculated. The formation curve was plotted between $\bar{n}A$ and $p\text{H}$ extending over a range $0.35 > \bar{n}A > 0.90$. This indicates the formation of species HL only. The value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half integral point $\bar{n}A = 0.5$. From the straight line plot of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}A}{1 - \bar{n}A} \right)$ against $p\text{H}$, the pK_1^H was also determined. This value agrees with that obtained by half integral method.

The maximum value of \bar{n} obtained in the $p\text{H}$ region where hydrolysis of metal ions is negligible is between 1.5 and 2.0 and revealed that metal-ligand ratio in the complexes is 1 : 2. The metal ligand stability constants were obtained from the formation curves (\bar{n} and pL), by plotting pL vs $\log \left(\frac{1 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n}} \right)$ for $\log K_1$ and pL vs $\log \left(\frac{2 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n} - 1} \right)$ for $\log K_2$. Log K values are given in Table 1 and follows the order $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$ in agreement with Irving-Williams order³.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

	Temp. $30 \pm 1^\circ$					
	$\mu = 0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$					
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Cd^{2+}
$\log K_1$	4.37	9.56	8.55	7.68	7.51	7.21
$\log K_2$	—	4.80	4.23	3.27	3.12	3.05

* For H^+ , K_1 corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 corresponds to species ML and ML_2 , respectively.

The complexation reactions are as follows :

Acknowledgement

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Spectrophotometric Studies on Dimethyl Tin Dichloride with PAN, Quinalizarin, Alizarin Red S, Solochrome Black and Methyl Oxine

S. B. SAXENA* and (Miss) CHHAYA SAXENA

Post-graduate Department of Chemistry, Madhav Institute of Technology and Science, Gwalior

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THE composition, structure and stability constants of many chelates have been determined by using mole ratio method, Job's method of continuous variation and slope ratio method. Pilloni¹, on the basis of spectrophotometric measurements, concluded complexation between PAN and a few organo-metallic moieties such as $\text{R}_2\text{Sn}(\text{II})$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ in dioxane. Many authors²⁻⁴ have done a number of similar studies in the recent past.

The present work was undertaken to extend the above investigations using following systems in 95% ethanol as a solvent.

Systems :

1. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN).
2. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 1,2,5,8-tetrahydroxy anthraquinone (Quinalizarin).
3. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 1,2-dihydroxy-3-anthraquinone sulphonic acid-Na Salt (Alizarin red S).

* Author for correspondence.

4. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and sodium (1-hydroxy-2-naphthylazo)-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (Solochrome black).
5. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 2-Methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (Methyl oxine)..

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used throughout the investigation. Double distilled ethanol (95%) was used as solvent. Absorbance measurement were made on Beckmann UV double beam spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cell at a fixed temperature of $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

The dyes used behave as colloidal electrolytes. Their extremely dilute solutions in the concentration range of 10^{-8} to $10^{-4}M$ in double distilled ethanol were therefore used. Stock solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3}M$) of the ligands and the Lewis acid [$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$] were also prepared in the same solvent. Solutions of requisite concentration were obtained by dilution with ethanol and used for spectrophotometric investigations.

Composition of the complexes :

The composition of the complexes was determined by mole ratio method⁵ and Job's⁶ method of continuous variation.

Mole ratio method :

In this method a solution containing a fixed amount of ligand in ethanol is spectrophotometrically titrated against increasing concentration of the Lewis acid in ethanol. 3.0 ml of the ligand solution ($1 \times 10^{-3}M$ for Alizarin red S, $0.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ for Quinalizarin, $2 \times 10^{-4}M$ for PAN, $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ for Methyl oxine and $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ for Solochrome black) was mixed with increasing volume of the solution of the Lewis acid (0.5 ml to 6.0 ml) of the same concentration as that of the ligand. The total volume was kept as 10.0 ml. The absorbances were measured at the λ_{max} of the respective complex. The values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION DATA IN 95% ETHANOL FOR THE LIGANDS AND THEIR ORGANOTIN COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Lewis base	Lewis acid moiety	λ_{max} nm	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \times 10^4$	Colour of the complex
1.	PAN	—	480	0.066	Yellow
	PAN	+ $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$	540	0.993	Red
2.	Quinalizarin	—	510	0.680	Light violet
	Quinalizarin	+ $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$	540	1.090	Reddish pink
3.	Alizarin red S	—	490	0.143	Light yellow
	Alizarin red S	+ $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$	475	0.243	Yellowish orange
4.	Solochrome black	—	580	0.383	Red
	Solochrome black	+ $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$	625	1.730	Blue
5.	Methyl oxine	—	—	0.00	Colourless
	Methyl oxine	+ $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$	360	0.163	Light yellow

Job's method of continuous variation :

The stock solutions of the ligands are diluted upto the required concentration ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$ for Alizarin red S and Quinalizarin, $5 \times 10^{-5}M$ for PAN, $6 \times 10^{-4}M$ for methyl oxine and $5 \times 10^{-5}M$ for Solochrome black). Solutions containing varying amounts of Lewis acid moiety $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}^{2+}$ (0.0 ml to 10 ml) were mixed with 10 to 0.0 ml of equimolar solutions of ligands and absorbances measured. Results are depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Job's method of continuous variation.

Colour of the complexes and the effect of time on the colour :

On mixing the ligand with Lewis acid, the colour developed instantaneously and there was no change in the absorbance value for 24 hr. The specific changes in colour have been recorded in Table 1. Order of mixing also has no effect on the absorbance values.

Results and Discussion

System— $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and PAN : The data obtained suggest formation of 1:1 complex. The rare possibility of existence of charged complexes in non-aqueous solvents and well established action of PAN⁷⁻⁹ behaving as a tridentate ligand leads to the conclusion that in the initial stages the complex exists mostly in the form A which is neutral and contains

hepta coordinated tin with two five membered rings and may be in equilibrium with the structure B [Chart (1)]. Although it is not certain as to which of the structure is stable under what conditions, apparently at low pH values species A is likely to be more stable while at higher pH the other species may be expected to be predominant.

System— $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ and Quinalizarin, and Alizarin red S: The data are in conformity with 1 : 1 complex. There are two possibilities of chelation. The chelation may occur from the quinoid oxygen atom and adjacent phenolic oxygen or with the two adjacent phenolic oxygens. The probable arrangements are shown in [Chart (2)].

System— $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ and Solochrome black 6-B : From the experimental data it is clear that Solochrome black 6-B behaves as a tridentate Lewis base and its interaction with the Lewis acid $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ results in the formation of chelates of structure shown in [Chart (3)] with hepta coordinated tin. The structures containing two rings, one with five members and the other with six members are likely to exist in equilibrium with the other two structures formed by the elimination of HCl molecule. The structures are pH dependent.

System— $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ and Methyl oxine : The absorption data of the complexes suggest that the

ligand acts as bidentate chelating agent. Its interaction with $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ takes place in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The structure [Chart (4)] may be formulated for the complex which gives rise to hexa coordinated tin atom with five membered ring. Another structure is possible due to the elimination of HCl molecule which is expected in presence of a base. In such a case the mole ratio between Lewis acid and Lewis base would be 1 : 2 which shall be contrary to experimental results.

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Reaction of the Cobaltic Ion. The Kinetics of the Reaction of Cobalt(III) with n-Valeric Acid

DINESH CHANDRA BUDHOLIA and J. K. STHAPAK
Department of Chemistry, Government Engineering College, Jabalpur

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THE kinetics of oxidation of a few saturated aliphatic acids with electrolytically prepared cobalt(III) has been studied by Clifford and Waters¹ in methylcyanide-water system. We report here our findings for the reaction of Co(III) with n-valeric acid in aqueous sulphuric acid.

The experimental procedure is similar to the one reported earlier².

Effect of different concentrations of n-valeric and sulphuric acids on the rate of loss of cobalt(III) : The effect of different concentrations of sulphuric acid on the rate of consumption of cobalt(III) in presence of three different concentrations of the organic acid at three temperatures has been investigated. It has been observed that the order of reaction with respect to Co(III) is one as the data could be fitted into the first order rate equation. The order of reaction with respect to the organic acid is fractional.

Chart—Probable structural formulae of complexes.